

A Cognitive Task Analysis-based Evaluation of Remotely Piloted Aircraft Situation Awareness Transfer Mechanisms

John P. Machuca, Michael E. Miller, John M. Colombi

Department of Systems and Engineering Management, Air Force Institute of Technology
Wright-Patterson AFB, OH. 45433 USA

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Abstract— Over the past several decades, the military, government and commercial industries have begun to realize the potential benefits that Remotely Piloted Aircraft (RPA) technologies stand to deliver. As a result, the demand for medium to high-altitude RPA operations, especially within the US Air Force, continues to grow. However, the assets and requisite resources to support those operations are far from unlimited and struggle to keep pace. This situation has inevitably led innovators to seek out RPA force-multiplying efficiencies to assist in bridging the resource/demand gap. One such consideration is simultaneous control of multiple aircraft by a single pilot, or Multi Aircraft Control (MAC). Past research has identified several challenges to MAC, to include dynamic and emergency task saturation, communications interruptions, and effective transfer of operational situation awareness (SA) from a losing crew to a gaining crew – called “change-over”. This (poster) paper describes the cognitive tasks, modalities, and transfer mechanisms to best achieve operational Situation Awareness (SA) within RPA operations, focusing on crew change-over. Using information from a Cognitive Task Analysis, tools, tactics and protocols to expedite and improve the change-over process will be identified and analyzed.

Index Terms— Man machine systems, Human factors, Cognitive informatics, Cognitive Task Analysis, Situation Awareness

I. INTRODUCTION

THE application of modern semi-autonomous Remotely Piloted Aircraft (RPA) and the long duration flight they have enabled has improved battle space Situation Awareness (SA) dramatically. This improvement in SA has been achieved with a relatively inexpensive and expendable platform. As such Department of Defense (DoD) leaders see the technology as a strategic solution to the omnipresent requirement to find

new ways to do far more with far less. Battlefield commanders relish the thought of persistent and detailed real-time knowledge of activities on the battlefield while strategically deploying limited ground resources. Today’s front-line warrior yearns for the substantial tactical advantages of more timely and effective close air support (CAS) from their RPA escorts. At all levels, RPA technologies have become imperative to modern missions, and there is little doubt that the robotic extension of the human warfighter has changed the way battles are waged and won. Of course, to perpetually further the state of a technological art, significant resources must be expended. In today’s fiscal reality, this simply is not feasible. And so the question within the DoD becomes how do we maximize the utility of our current RPA capabilities, without expending large quantities of already very limited resources?

To answer this question, it is important to consider that RPAs are part of a complex system-of-systems. The system has many components including one or more air vehicles, ground control stations (GCS) for both primary mission control and takeoff/landing, a communications suite (including intercom, chat, radios, phones, a satellite link, etc), support equipment, intelligence, command, and operations and maintenance crews [1] which are distributed globally. Assets and resources to support operations are limited and personnel resources, particularly RPA pilots, sensor operators, and Mission Intelligence Coordinators (MICs), often prove a nontrivial constraint. This challenge has lead innovators to seek out RPA force-multiplying efficiencies to assist in bridging the resource/demand gap. Multiple Aircraft Control (MAC) is one such identified efficiency. MAC is defined as the simultaneous control of multiple aircraft, and is typically discussed from the pilot’s point of view, but applies equally to the MIC. The MAC concept of operations has been documented by the US Air Force [2] which envisions future single pilots will simultaneously control multiple RPAs. Similar plans might be called out for the remainder of the crew, including the pilot and MIC. Such a construct facilitates a flying squadron to do more with less - at least in terms of two of the mostly highly constrained resources, pilots and MICs.

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When considering MAC, past research has identified several challenges to include dynamic and emergency task saturation, communications interruptions, and effective and efficient transfer of operational SA from a losing pilot to a gaining pilot [3]. This SA transfer occurs at the conclusion of a typical shift and is termed “change-over”. Analyses have concluded that change-over activities can consume up to 10% of a pilot’s mission time [3]. In a MAC scenario, if a pilot accepts control of three or four aircraft, the subsequent transfer time and effort can balloon to consume an unreasonable percentage of the pilot’s effective mission time. Such a reduction in mission time runs counter to the intended objectives of MAC implementation.

Similar challenges are hypothesized for SA transfer amongst gaining and losing MICs at change-over. In many ways, the MIC operates as the communication focal point and information integrator within the GCS. He or she communicates with and filters information from numerous internal and external entities and in turn provides integrated information to the pilot and other crew members as needed and as appropriate. Because of this role and the substantial number of parties that the MIC must interact with during the span of a given mission, there are large numbers and types of communicated data points that must be transferred to an on-coming MIC prior to assuming control for their SA to be operationally satisfactory.

Towards overcoming this challenge, the cognitive tasks, modalities, and transfer mechanisms imposed by the complexity of achieving operational SA on multiple aircraft is examined. This paper describes research that will utilize a Cognitive Task Analysis (CTA) to identify the goals, decisions and corresponding information requirements of RPA MICs to transfer operational SA during change-over. Using this information tools, tactics and protocols intended to expedite or improve the change-over process will be identified, analyzed and compared, thereby potentially increasing mission effectiveness and RPA availability in single aircraft control, as well as providing conclusions relevant to the eventual successful implementation of MAC.

II. BACKGROUND

A. Situation Awareness

Endsley defines Situation Awareness (SA) as “the perception of the elements in the environment within a volume of time and space, the comprehension of their meaning and the projection of their status in the near future” [4]. Further, she describes three discrete levels of SA – perception, comprehension, and projection. The first level, perception, considers the capture of critical factors or data points describing the environment. Integrating those factors into a cohesive understanding of the situation constitutes the second level of SA. The third and highest level of SA is using the information from the previous two levels to project into the future how the situation might change and preparing contingency plans of these changes.

At the heart of any definition of SA is the comparison between actual system status and the operator’s perception and

understanding of system status [5]. As this gap widens, SA deteriorates. As it closes, SA becomes more complete and actionable.

Maintaining sound and complete SA is a task of paramount importance to any vehicle operator. Without sufficient understanding of one’s physical surroundings, system location and orientation (in all three axes), system state of health (SOH), the location and profile of threats and allies, and so on, an operator has little to no hope of successfully completing an assigned task, or perhaps even surviving the mission. Considering the fact that a military aircraft typically operates several miles above terra firma, to say that an aircrew must work diligently to maintain sound SA is a dramatic understatement. Any decision made during a lapse of SA, even a momentary one, can quickly result in catastrophic consequences. A review by Hartel, Smith and Prince in 1991 [6] found SA to be the leading causal factor of military aviation mishaps. Of major air carrier accidents involving human error, 88% could be attributed to SA failures per a report conducted by Endsley in 1994 [7]. These dangers are dramatically asseverated when the operator is removed from the vehicle itself, as with RPAs. Physical disconnection from the system creates a host of additional SA issues for RPA crew to include lack of visual, auditory and tactile sensory cues, time lags between command issuance, vehicle response and feedback, “blind spots” in system status data, signal interruption, degradation or loss, sensor malfunctions, and system interface challenges to include the ongoing mental task of creating a fused sight picture from disparate data sources. Riley & Endsley [8] expand this list adding “out-of-the-loop syndrome”, mode awareness problems, and vigilance decrements to the SA challenges faced by RPA crews.

Having discussed the extreme importance and substantial challenge SA maintenance poses for RPA crew the operational value of the present effort to assist with initial SA achievement at change-over becomes evident.

B. Change-over

Specific US Air Force RPAs have sustainable loiter times greater than 24 hours. Couple that with the fact that these military RPA crews typically limit operation time to 2-3 hour intervals [3], and it becomes clear that change-overs, being defined as the transfer of RPA control from a losing crew to a gaining crew, are a very common process that often occurs multiple times during the course of any given mission. In fact, a single aircrew frequently completes more than one change-over in a day. In terms of duration and therefore operational impact, analysis has shown that change-overs can account for 8-20% of total mission time in single aircraft control, and have been projected to require as much as 40% of total mission time if a MAC of four was employed [3]. When you consider its frequency, duration, and impact on mission success, change-over is a phase of RPA operation that deserves rigorous analysis and disciplined efforts towards optimization.

The change-over process is typically detailed as four distinct tasks: the gaining (on-coming) crewmembers receive a pre-

mission brief from the mission support cell (MSC), the loosing aircrew provides individualized change-over briefs to the gaining crew, “nest building” takes place, the gaining crew members complete the on-coming crew brief while the losing crew accomplishes post-flight tasks. The accuracy of this protocol, particularly with respect to pilots and MICs, is corroborated by change-overs witnessed and discussions held with active duty crews at during 2011.

Task 1 – Gaining crew receives pre-mission brief from mission support cell

Approximately 15 minutes prior to the scheduled change-over time, the MSC provides the gaining crew with a pre-mission brief to educate them on pertinent mission data (mission assignment, intelligence reports, weather reports, etc), Rules of Engagement (ROEs) and recent mission events and developments. This step is intended to provide the on-coming crew with the essential elements of information (EIs) needed to achieve sufficient SA prior to assuming control of the aircraft.

Task 2 – Loosing aircrew provides change-over brief to gaining crew members

When the gaining pilot or MIC arrives to the GCS from the MSC, the loosing pilot or MIC provides the change-over briefing to their gaining counterpart. Typically, losing aircrew utilize checklists, handwritten flight logs/notes and current vehicle displays to provide a verbal brief of all mission and vehicle EIs. For the pilot, one such checklist prompts to brief weather, clearance data (airspace, altitude blocks, other aircraft in the area, etc), current datalink configurations, emergency mission info (waypoints, altitudes, lost link headings, etc), operational mission status, target information (to include weapons status), and aircraft status (fuel, glide speed, anomalies, write ups).

Task 3 – Nest Building

At this point the on-coming crewmember has officially assumed control of the active work station and goes about “nest building”. Nest building includes configuring the station and certain system settings to their personal preferences, checking the status of pertinent systems and performing communication checks. This must be accomplished quickly and carefully. Once completed, the change-over process has officially been accomplished.

Task 4 – Gaining crew completes the on-coming crew brief while the losing accomplishes post-flight tasks

The departing crew completes requisite post-mission tasks immediately following their delivery of the change-over brief to the gaining crew. This usually occurs in the squadron operations center or in an available briefing room. Discussions typically center around maintenance issues, lessons learned, any aircraft or GCS issues, and any applicable after action reports to be filed. During this time, the new crew completes their own pre-mission crew brief in the GCS. This is typically a high-level discussion reviewing key items identified in the

previous steps and some discussion of task allocation.

The analysis that this paper describes shall be focused on identifying potential tools or techniques to better facilitate the second step in the change-over process for the MIC.

C. Cognitive Task Analysis

Borne of the applied psychology field, CTA is a broadly applied and often customized kit of tools and techniques used for the identification and description of the knowledge and strategies needed for task accomplishment. Per Shraagen et al, “Cognitive task analysis is the extension of traditional task analysis techniques to yield information about the knowledge, thought processes, and goal structures that underlie observable task performance.” [9]. While CTA has numerous manifestations, structures and levels of formality, typically the process can be described as five steps which are briefly discussed in the following paragraphs.

At the outset, preliminary data collection should be accomplished. The intention of this first step is for the analyst to become familiarized with the domain and process being studied and includes the identification of key cognitive tasks, with particular attention paid to those tasks that are difficult, frequent or highly critical cognitive tasks within the job. To achieve these ends, a few of the tools and techniques at the analyst’s disposal include literature review, observations and unstructured interviews. At the conclusion of this effort it is generally beneficial to visually depict any results, often in the form of concept maps or the like describing the relationship between tasks, subtasks and information requirements. The creation of such knowledge representations is the second step of the procedure.

With a education of the domain, the process and its tasks attained and represented, the analyst can then begin the third step of a more intelligent and focused investigation of the EIs by implementing applied knowledge elicitation methods which include interviews, both unstructured and structured, verbal protocol walkthroughs and the critical decision method (see [10] for additional information on the critical decision method). Of these, unstructured and structured interviews are most commonly selected as they require little training and are relatively easy to employ and customize to the desired level of investigative formality.

Next the analyst must take the information that has been collected thus far and categorize and synthesize it into meaningful conclusions. As part of this fourth step, the resultant data should be refined, packaged and presented in an intuitive way to facilitate taking the synthesized information and conclusions and providing it to subject matter experts to have the data validated and verified for its intended purpose. With the data and resultant conclusions validated and verified, the yield of actionable information to inform intelligent system design will have been delivered.

The fifth and final step of the CTA is to take the achieved results and to translate them into meaningful and informative models which should “reveal the underlying skills, mental models, and problem-solving strategies used by experts when performing highly complex tasks.” [11] These models can

then be used to inform curriculum, training procedures and system design.

III. METHODOLOGY

The methodology of this analysis includes four phases – conduct a CTA of the MIC change-over process; use the products of the CTA to envision multiple system definitions to better facilitate change-over; measure and compare the effectiveness of those system definitions; draw meaningful conclusions and recommendations. Each of these phases are further discussed in the following paragraphs.

A. Cognitive Task Analysis of Change-over Process

To accomplish the preliminary data collection phase of the CTA on the MIC's SA transfer at change-over a robust literature review followed by initial unstructured interviews and operational observations of active duty US Air Force MICs were accomplished at Creech Air Force Base in September of 2011. The second step of creating knowledge representations to describe the tasks, subtasks and information requirements observed is nearing completion. In preparation for the third step of the CTA, structured and unstructured interviews will be built with CTA design principles in mind to arrive to the root of the needed information for an oncoming MIC to gain complete and operational SA of an in-flight RPA, so as to inform the analysis and comparison of potential system designs being evaluated to improve the change-over process. In accordance with the previously described fourth step, all data and conclusions will be packaged and presented to RPA subject matter experts for validation and verification purposes. With this accomplished the results can be presented so as to best posture the CTA data to inform the intelligent comparison of envisioned change-over facilitating system definitions.

B. Envision Multiple System Definitions for Change-over

With the CTA accomplished the particular data points (EEIs) that a MIC must be aware of to gain operational SA on an aircraft will have been explicitly identified and presented. From here, an improved picture can be formed of the characteristics necessary for any new system definition to be able to better facilitate SA transfer. With these design characteristics in mind, several potential tools and/or procedures shall be selected for cross-comparison to determine if they would indeed improve the change-over process, and if so, by how much and in what way.

C. Measure SA Transfer Effectiveness of System Definitions

With new system definitions identified, an analysis shall be conducted to determine which of these definitions is most useful to facilitate change-over, independently or in concert with current methods or other new system definitions.

With phases A-C accomplished, meaningful conclusions and recommendations will be able to be drawn and presented to the RPA community.

IV. CONCLUSION

The overarching goal of this effort is to increase RPA mission effectiveness and availability by way of providing RPA crews with an improved ability to transfer SA at change-over faster, better, and preferably with reduced cognitive effort. To do this, careful consideration must be paid in determining what exact data points must be exchanged for the recipient to have sound and operationally actionable SA on an RPA. Then, and only then, can one begin to see what an improved change-over system could like and how it may operate. These newly envisioned system definitions must then be quantitatively tested, analyzed and compared to determine their suitability towards the goal of the research, before any concluding recommendations can be presented to the RPA community. By employing CTA on the front end to ensure a robust examination of change-over relevant data, this effort shall be able to provide verifiable, validatable and meaningful conclusions towards advancing the state-of-the-art of RPA operations in today's resource constrained environment.

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